

Mitral Regurgitation and Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth in Dogs: A Co-morbidity or Consequence of ‘Gut-Heart Axis’^A

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Abstract: Small intestinal bacterial overgrowth (SIBO) is a clinical condition characterised by the presence of colon-derived bacteria in the small intestine at a density of $\geq 10^5$ CFU/mL. Congestive heart failure (CHF) causes structural and functional changes in the gastrointestinal tract and has been associated with increased bacterial colonisation, inflammation and malabsorption. A total of 7 dogs with different stages of mitral valve disease and congestive heart failure were included in the study. All dogs were evaluated by clinical examination, laboratory tests involving relevant cardiopulmonary biomarkers and echocardiography. Lactulose-based breath test (LBT) test was used for SIBO and 16S rRNA gene sequencing was used for intestinal microbiota analysis. In the result, *Peptoclostridium* sp. was identified as the most frequently detected species in the fecal microbiota of dogs with congestive heart failure due to mitral regurgitation. In all cases, an increase of ≥ 20 ppm compared to the baseline value was observed in the LBT, which was evaluated in favor of SIBO. The most significant increase in hydrogen levels was noted at 60 and 90 minutes. In conclusion, CHF is closely associated with gut microbiota and intestinal dysbiosis should be evaluated in cases of heart disease.

Keywords: Small intestinal bacterial overgrowth, Chronic heart failure, Myxoid mitral valve disease, Dysbiosis

^A The study does not require approval from an ethics committee. The article has been prepared according to research and publication ethics.

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Introduction

Small intestinal bacterial overgrowth (SIBO) is a clinical condition characterised by the presence of colon-derived bacteria in the small intestine at a density of $\geq 10^5$ CFU/mL. It is associated with the overgrowth of *Streptococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Bacteroides*, *Lactobacillus*, and some *Enterobacteriaceae* species and can lead to gastrointestinal symptoms such as bloating, gas, abdominal pain, and diarrhoea. Nutrient deficiencies may develop as a result of malabsorption and increased lipopolysaccharide (LPS) permeability may trigger chronic inflammation and cause systemic effects. Although jejunal aspirate culture is the gold standard for diagnosis, glucose (GBT), and LBT are more commonly used (Sroka et al., 2023; Adike and DiBaise, 2018; Roland et al., 2014; Pimentel et al., 2020). Unlike SIBO, intestinal methanogen overgrowth (IMO) is associated with archaeons (*Methanobrevibacter smithii*) rather than bacteria. These organisms produce methane using hydrogen and cause constipation, bloating and intestinal motility disorders. IMO is also diagnosed by GBT or LBT, while a methane level of ≥ 10 ppm is considered diagnostic. The most effective treatment is the combination of rifaximin and neomycin, which reduces methane levels more than antibiotic use alone (Madihan et al., 2022; O'Dwyer, 2021; Pimentel et al., 2003; Low et al., 2010).

Congestive heart failure (CHF) causes structural and functional changes in the gastrointestinal tract and has been associated with increased bacterial colonisation, inflammation and malabsorption (Romeiro et al., 2012). Small intestinal oedema causes a decrease in nutrient absorption, impairs enterocyte function and predisposes to the development of SIBO (Sandek et al., 2007). Systemic inflammation is stimulated due to bacterial translocation and increased intestinal permeability, and the process increases the severity of CHF (Yndestad et al., 2006). Endoscopic examination of the gastrointestinal tract reveals thickening of the intestinal mucosa and vascular changes due to malabsorption and gastrointestinal bleeding in patients with CHF (Raja et al., 2004). Viscero-sensory reflexes may change in relation with the complications of hypoperfusion and portal congestion due to congestive heart failure and abdominal symptoms may occur as a result (Sandek et al., 2007). However, changes in intestinal motility may play a leading role in the development of both SIBO and IMO (Linz et al., 2017). IMO due to metagenic arches is reported to play a role in increasing the severity of constipation in CHF patients (Rychik, 2020; Madihan et al., 2022). It adversely affects the prognosis of CHF by causing the development of protein loss enteropathy and consequently hypoproteinaemia associated with malabsorption and intestinal oedema, which are digestive problems (Sundaram and Fang, 2016). In these patients, it is important to prefer drugs with high bioavailability and long half-life. As an example, it has been reported that torsemide with diuretic effect reduces the risk of hospitalisation in CHF patients and contributes more positively to the management of functional impairment in the heart compared to furosemide (Theis and Turner, 2020; Pimentel et al., 2003). Myxomatous mitral valve disease (MMVD) is a common cardiac problem in dogs described by mitral valve degeneration (Buchanan, 1999; Borgelli and Buchanan, 2012). The disease might primarily have an asymptomatic stage and then become clinically visible with signs of CHF (Keene et al., 2019). Studies have reported that metabolic routes associated to gut microbiota might play a role in the pathogenesis of MMVD and CHF. Trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO) levels in blood and other toxic compounds are increased in dogs with both MMVD and CHF. These alterations shed light on the heart and gut axis (Karlin et al., 2019; Li et al., 2021). TMAO is synthesized by intestinal microbiota and plays a dynamic role on the progression of disease by increasing systemic inflammation (Wang et al., 2011; Tang et al., 2019). The “leaky gut” term is characterized by damaged intestinal integrity and increased permeability situations. Leaky gut also allows the entry of bacterial metabolites into the blood circulation

and causes an increase of the systemic inflammatory states (Tang et al., 2019). In patients with CHF, imbalanced levels of short chain fatty acids and primary and secondary bile acids (BA) has been reported (Koeth et al., 2013; Lefebvre et al., 2009).

However, it is not yet known whether these changes are the cause or the results of the disease (Li et al., 2021). It has been reported that dysbiosis and stage of the disease increase in proportion to each other in dogs with MMVD. These changes are inversely proportional to bacteria that is responsible for the conversion of bile acids, such as *Clostridium hiranonis* (Li et al., 2021). An increase in the number of *E. coli*, a pathogenic species, also leads to an increase in TMAO levels. It is thought that it might expose new possibilities.

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between microbiota and heart failure in dogs diagnosed with SIBO and IMO by breath tests.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at the Aydin Adnan Menderes University, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Department of Internal Medicine. A total of seven dogs were included in the study with primarily MMVD and CHF at different stages. Routine clinical evaluations were performed on all dogs included in the study. In this study, cardiopulmonary biomarkers were used to determine the presence of heart disease. Echocardiographic measurements were performed to evaluate heart disease under criteria's that were determined in the 2019 guideline of the American College of Veterinary Internal Medicine (ACVIM) and were taken into account in determining presence and degree of disease. ACVIM classification, B1: Asymptomatic patients without remodeling, B2: Asymptomatic patients with advanced mitral valve insufficiency, C: Patients with clinical symptoms associated with CHF, D: Resistant to standard treatment.

Echocardiographic examination was performed to evaluate the severity of mitral regurgitation (MR) in patients with end stage CHF and they were divided into four groups according to the percentage of insufficient volume (ARJ/LAA): Mild (<30%), Moderate (30-50%), Severe (50-70%), Very Severe (>70%).

Diagnosis of SIBO and IMO with Breath Tests

The presence of SIBO and IMO were determined using the LBT. Before the test, all dogs were exposed to low glycemic index commercial food. As an inclusion criterion, dogs were fasted for 12 hours. For breath test, samples were collected at periodical time intervals (0. min, 30., 60., 90. min.), throughout the test. Hydrogen (H₂) and methane (CH₄) levels were measured according to device protocols. An increase of ≥ 20 ppm in basal hydrogen level was considered as a criterion for the diagnosis of SIBO, and an increase of ≥ 10 ppm in methane level at any time was considered as a criterion for the diagnosis of IMO.

Microbiota Analysis of Stool Samples

The intestinal microbiota profile was analysed by 16S rRNA sequencing on stool samples. Samples were collected under sterile conditions and stored at -80°C. DNA extraction and microbiota analysis were performed by the MiDOG Company through service procurement. Within the scope of the analysis, bacterial diversity and dysbiosis index were calculated and the abundance of specific intestinal bacteria such as *Clostridium hiranonis*, *E. coli* and bacterial groups associated with TMAO production were evaluated.

Statistical analyses

In this study, graphical presentation of numerical data was performed using R software (R Core Team, 2024) and RStudio interface. Gut microbiota data were presented clustered in bar graphs with the ggplot2 package, showing the relative abundance of bacterial species for each case. Likewise, LBT data were plotted against the time axis. The H₂ levels of each case were shown separately as a function of time and the diagnostic cut-off value of ≥ 20 ppm increase was indicated with a cut-off line on the graphs. Different color codes were used in all visualizations to differentiate cases.

Results

In this study, we examined the relative abundance of bacterial populations in fecal samples of dogs diagnosed with SIBO and congestive heart failure due to different stages of mitral regurgitation (MMVD). The percentages of bacterial species detected in the fecal microbiota profile of each case are presented as a clustered bar graph in Figure 1. The graph shows the distribution by case for each bacterial species separately.

Figure 1. Relative abundance of fecal bacterial species across individual cases with heart failure

Considering all cases, *Peptoclostridium sp.* was the most frequently detected species; this bacterium was detected at 17.3% in case 2. *Porphyromonas caniningivalis* was among the most dominant species with 11.6% in cases 5, 6 and 7. *Enterococcus casseliflavus* was found in 3.9% of cases 6 and 7. *Bacteroides pyogenes* was detected at varying levels in different cases, particularly in case 3 with 9.1%.

Some bacterial species were found in higher proportions only in certain cases. For example, *Trueperella abortusuis* was detected at 2.8-1.8% in cases 2, 6, and 7; *Clostridium perfringens* was detected at 3% only in Case 4. Other bacterial species such as *Finigoldia magna*, *Corynebacterium jeikeium*, *Propionibacterium acnes*, *Enterococcus hirae* were also found at low rates in some cases.

The LBT results of the seven dogs enrolled in the study were evaluated based on H₂ concentrations measured at 0, 30, 60, and 90 minutes. The time-dependent H₂ levels of each case are shown in Figure 2. In all cases analyzed, an increase of ≥ 20 ppm was detected in at least one of the subsequent time points compared to the baseline value (minute 0). This increase was considered above the threshold for the diagnosis of SIBO. Therefore, all cases were considered SIBO-positive. H₂ concentrations are shown along with the individual case curves and the cut-off line representing the diagnostic cut-off of 20 ppm increase is indicated on the graph by the dashed black line. It was observed that the most significant increase in H₂ levels occurred at 60 and 90 minutes in most cases.

Figure 2. Hydrogen breath test curves of seven SIBO-positive dogs with diagnostic cut-off line

Discussion

Congestive heart failure is a systemic process that affects not only cardiac functions but also the gastrointestinal system, and factors such as portal hypertension, intestinal edema, and visceral hypoperfusion disrupt the integrity of the intestinal mucosa, leading to malabsorption and inflammation (Ghoshal, 2011). This situation facilitates bacterial translocation and may accelerate the progression of CHF by increasing the severity of systemic inflammation (Fialho et al., 2016). It has also been reported that intestinal motility disorders associated with CHF may contribute to the development of both SIBO and IMO by increasing the accumulation of hydrogen and methane in the intestines (Niu et al., 2016). In our study, when the LBT results were examined, it was revealed that each of them showed presence of SIBO. In all cases, an increase of ≥ 20 ppm was detected compared to the initial hydrogen level, and this increase was found to be dominant at the 60th and 90th minutes and indicates that intestinal dysfunction due to CHF contributes to the development of SIBO. In human medicine, SIBO is also associated with a lot of systemic diseases such as diabetes mellitus (Malik et al., 2018), atherosclerosis (Ponziani et al., 2017), and coronary artery disease (He et al., 2018). When examined in these aspects, our study is considered to be a pioneering study that revealed the interaction between CHF and SIBO in dogs. Significant structural changes such as mucosal thickening, antral vascular ectasia, telangiectatic areas, and intestinal wall edema were observed in the stomach, ileum, colon, and sigmoid regions and have been identified in endoscopic examinations in patients with CHF (Raja et al., 2004; Sandek et al., 2007). Studies suggest that the thickness of the sigmoid colon is positively correlated with the leukocyte count and high-sensitive CRP levels might trigger systemic inflammation. Furthermore, findings such as increased distance between the basal membrane of enterocytes and capillary vessels and increased collagen content indicates the presence of pathological structural alterations that directly affect intestinal absorption (Sandek et al., 2007; Arutyunov et al., 2008).

In our study, in seven dogs with MMVD secondary to CHF, gut microbiota analysis showed that bacteria such as *Peptoclostridium spp.*, *Porphyromonas caniningivalis*, *Enterococcus casseliflavus* became significantly dominant and found in greater abundance. The predominance of *Peptoclostridium* especially in Case 2 and *Porphyromonas* dominance in many cases support that the bacterial balance in intestine is disrupted with the progression of CHF. These results suggest that CHF might increase bacterial colonization and biofilm formation by affecting intestinal epithelial organization and defense mechanisms.

In endoscopic studies in humans, it has been reported that bacterial adhesion to the mucosa increased to 70% and biofilm covered regions reached 35% in patients with CHF (in control groups, these rates were 36% and 10%, respectively; $p < 0.01$) (Sandek et al., 2007). In our study, although no direct endoscopy was performed, LBT showed an increase of ≥ 20 ppm H_2 in all cases, indicating that microbial accumulation in the small intestine and indirectly the bacterial gas production increased at the clinical level. When evaluated together with these findings, it could be assumed that microbial dysbiosis in dogs with CHF is accompanied by structural changes and increased intestinal permeability. It has also been suggested in previous studies that these disruptions in intestinal epithelium might contribute to protein loss, malabsorption and ultimately cardiac cachexia (Boyd et al., 1993; Johnston et al., 1996; Anker et al., 1997).

Changes in gut microbiota in CHF patients have become an important research topic in recent years.

In a study, increases in the numbers of pathogenic bacteria *Campylobacter*, *Shigella*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Candida spp.* were detected in people with CHF. In the aforementioned study, there were also reports of an increase in intestinal permeability (IP) and gastrointestinal inflammation biomarkers (Pasini et al., 2016). It is emphasized that these elevated alterations occurs along with cardiac function and that might be related to venous congestion and systemic inflammation (Pasini et al., 2016). In another veterinary study, it was reported that dogs with CHF had altered relative abundances of Proteobacteria phylum, especially the Enterobacteriaceae family and pathogenic species such as *E. coli* (Seo et al., 2020). This aforementioned study also reported higher rates of some bacterial groups such as *Roseburia*, *Parabacteroides*, *Enterococcaceae* in dogs with CHF. This suggests that the dysbiosis profile described in humans develops similarly in dogs with CHF (Seo et al., 2020). In our study, 16S rRNA based gut microbiota analysis were conducted to dogs with CHF and in a few cases bacterias of *Peptoclostridium spp.*, *Porphyromonas canigingivalis* and *Enterococcus casseliflavus* enhanced dominant, while higher abundance rates of *Clostridium perfringens* and *Trueperella abortusuis* were detected in limited number of cases. It is possible to associate this bacterial diversity and dominant abundance of pathogenic species with intestinal epithelial damage, increased mucosal permeability and malabsorption in dogs with CHF. In particular, in our study, all cases were SIBO positive with LBT and dysbiotic structures were detected in the gut microbiota profile, suggesting that the intestinal microbiota and immune system axis might be disrupted in dogs with CHF.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it was determined that intestinal microbiota was impaired in dogs with CHF and this was associated with SIBO. The predominance of pathogenic bacteria in faecal samples indicates that the intestinal barrier is weakened and the microbial balance is disrupted. The increase in hydrogen levels indicates that the intestinal microbiota is impaired and bacterial overgrowth is clinically effective. This might be two-way traffic regarding 'gut-heart axis' rather than a comorbidity, it might be concluded that one route of disease activity (probably within the intestines) could have influence on other (within the cardiac route). It has been observed that CHF may increase systemic inflammation by impairing intestinal functions. The data obtained show that the relationship between heart and intestine should also be considered in the veterinary field. In this respect, the study provides an important basis for further research.

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